

Paper Title: PEM4PPM: A Cognitive Perspective on the Process of Process Mining
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Participants' Demographics

For both the students and the experienced analysts, we collected demographic data through a demographic questionnaire.

A summary of the collected information for the 16 students is shown in **Table 1**.

S#	Gender
3	F
8	F
4	M
9	F
5	F
10	F
7	M
2	M
1	M
6	M
13	F
14	F
15	F
12	M
16	F
11	F

Table 1: Demographics of the 16 students.

S#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection. **Gender:** the participant's gender
M - male, F - female.

A summary of the collected information for the 13 experienced analysts is shown in **Table 2**.

E#	Sector	Current Role	Experience (yrs)		Expertise	#Projects	#Tools	#Logs
			Process Mining	Data Science	Process Mining			
3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	3	> 10	Good	2 - 5	2	> 10
6	Freelance	Process Mining Consultant	2	1-3	Good	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
7	Academia	Professor	10	6-10	Advanced	6 -10	3	> 10
10	Academia	Senior Researcher	1	1	Novice	None	1	2 - 5
11	Freelance	Business Analyst	8	> 10	Advanced	6 -10	4	6 - 10
16	Academia	PhD Student	4	None	Average	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
22	Academia	Graduate Student	0.3	1-3	Basic	1	1	2 - 5
26	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	7	1-3	Good	2 - 5	1	2 - 5
28	Academia	Professor	4	> 10	Good	2 - 5	4	> 10
29	Academia	PhD Student	6	6-10	Good	2 - 5	5	> 10
30	Academia	Professor	10	1-3	Average	2 - 5	5	2 - 5
34	Government	Consultant	10	> 10	Good	6 -10	2	2 - 5
35	Insurance	Business Analyst	2	1-3	Good	2 - 5	1	2 - 5

Table 2: Demographics of the 13 experienced analysts.

E#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection. **Sector:** the sector to which the participant's affiliation/company belongs. **Current Role:** the participant's job role at the time of the data collection. **Experience (yrs):** years of experience in process mining and data science or analytics. **Expertise:** Self-reported expertise in process mining; a Likert scale with values Novice, Basic, Average, Good and Advanced was used. **#Projects:** the number of process mining having the main goal of analyzing process data for a customer/company. **#Tools:** the number of process mining tools that the participant can use. **#Logs:** the number of event logs analyzed in the past two years.

Interview Protocols

Interview protocol used for students

1. Why did you choose to use this tool during the session?
2. Do you think your tool knowledge was sufficient for performing the task?
3. How familiar are you with the process of managing or receiving traffic fines?
4. Did you understand the process and the rules that describe it?
5. Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today?
6. Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how, when and why?
7. Would you follow the same analysis approach having this session again?
8. Is there anything that you found challenging to analyze today? If so, describe a challenge you faced and how you overcame it. What do you think was the cause of the challenge? What do you think can help you to overcome it?
9. Have you experienced any difficulties related to the functionality of the tool?
10. Is there any particular tool functionality you were missing?
11. Did you receive results or findings that you did not expect to receive at any stage of your analysis? How did you deal with it? What is the reason for this?
12. Did you experience difficulty in deciding how to move forward at any stage of analysis?
13. In your opinion, did you experience any personal challenge (a challenge that is just for you, not for other participants) while performing the task? If so, please describe it.
14. How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis?
15. Did you want to receive feedback during the meeting?
16. Did you feel pressured being watched?

Interview protocol for experienced analysts

(T): To be asked referring to the process mining task

(G): To be asked referring to general work practices

ACTIVITIES, TARGET ARTIFACTS and USE of ARTIFACTS

- Can you briefly summarize the main steps of your analysis today and explain why you worked in this way ? (T)
- Would you always follow the same steps in practice? (G)
- What information did you aim to gather during the analysis? Why? (T)
- Would you always focus on gathering the same information in practice or does that change from case to case? (G)
- How did you use the provided artifacts during the analysis? Why were they useful? (T)

GOALS

- Can you summarize the main goals of your analysis today? (T)
- Do you always work with these goals in mind in practice? (G)
- Do you always have clear analysis goals or objectives in practice? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that the analyses you conduct in practice are exploratory? By exploratory we mean that you spend time refining research questions, generating new questions for the analysis.

STRATEGIES

- Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today? (T)
- Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how? (T)
- Would you follow the same approach in practice, with other event logs? (G)
- How did you decide where to start your analysis from? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually choose where to start your analysis from? (G)
- How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis? Did you follow any criteria? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually decide that it is time to stop the analysis? (G)

CHALLENGES

- Is there anything that you found challenging during the task today? (T)
- And in general, what do you think are the biggest challenges of process mining? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that good tool knowledge helps to overcome process mining challenges? (G)
- Do you think that combining different process mining tools is an opportunity for the analysis or do you think it is too complicated/not needed? (G)
- Taking a look at process mining, where do you think there is more need for methodological or operational support? (G)

Data Analysis and Findings

Analysis and Findings for RQ1

One of the findings of the paper is the PEM4PPM v2 model including its validated steps (see **Section 5** Subsection Qualitative analysis paragraph *Validated PEM4PPM model*). [Table 3](#) describes the cognitive steps of the PEM4PPM v2 model, and provides an explanation, including example statements from the participants, and detection method, i.e., what sources of data were used to identify it.

Cognitive step	Explanation	Example statement	Detection method
Task understanding	Understanding the task/problem, understanding the data (e.g., attributes, model, activities), verifying with researcher/stakeholder information regarding the data or task.	<p>"Wait, the question is about the fine or the additional penalty?" (S7)</p> <p>"So, the activities are here. I will spend one minute or two just looking at them. (E30)"</p> <p>"Yeah, I just was having a look at the question." (E26)</p> <p>"Can I ask you something? This is not a preprocessed event log... I mean, incomplete cases are in, right?" (E30)</p>	<p>Screen: Supporting materials, the question/task text.</p> <p>Possible keywords: Asking a question</p>
Set/Refine goal	Formulating a goal related to the question.	<p>"So, the question is to identify the flows where the payment has not been done completely. That is why now I isolate the flows, the different flows that we have..." (E26)</p>	Screen: NA
Focus	Concentrating on a specific part/activity of the map.	<p>"So I think that first of all, to focus on the cases in which there was the addition of a penalty, so I'm actually going to filter by this element {points to Add penalty}. (S3)</p> <p>"Let me see, I want to see the cases that are paid here and the cases that are paid here from which sources payments are done." (E6)</p>	<p>Screen: Filter or part of Map view</p> <p>Possible keywords: "look maybe a little bit closer...", "Let's zoom in a little bit more...", "Let's see the most cases..."</p>
Explore	Learning about the process.	<p>"He has a fine of 20, he has a fine of 22, he pays 22, then he had a penalty of 44. I don't understand why and then he paid another 35." (S8)</p> <p>"I have an overview of the payment with all the frequencies, absolute frequency, case frequency, maximum repetitions and frequency, which tells me uh how many cases is the end the last step of the process. So, in this case, the payment occurs in almost 7000 cases. Collection." (E22)</p>	<p>Screen: csv file, Map view, Explorer view (Variants), Statistics view</p>
Interpret data	Explaining the process based on	<p>"Yeah, this is, this is one third of the cases. Here it says 30% of the cases. We saw on</p>	<p>Screen: NA</p> <p>Possible keywords: "So,</p>

	previously inspected behaviors, information about the process, the participant's previous knowledge and experience, or their combination.	the diagram that it was one third. Oh, yeah. 30% is one third, about. Um, yeah, one third of the citizens are good [laughing]. I have never driven in Italy, but it doesn't look like people drive following the rules. And I think that the data confirms..." (E3)	I guess this...", "It could be the case...", "That means that...", "So maybe it was...", "it seems that...", "maybe...", "I suppose...", "this is interesting...", "But that is just how I interpret the, the process", "So, this tells me that...", "so this probably...", "I'm thinking from my experience that it's so...", "in my view...", "So, I know that from a similar domain..."
Create artifact	Producing deliverable objects driven by a goal.	"Ok. So, I save now the first scenario of the process." (E26) "Hmm. And it probably will make a difference, probably. Is it possible for me to make a screenshot of this and put it on the side?" (E3)	Screen: Screenshot of Filter, Statistics view, Map view; Saving/Persisting a specific scenario.
Generate hypotheses	Forming a hypothesis about previously identified behaviour or possible answers for the question.	"So, my first hypothesis is this, that the delays in sending the notifications is a very popular variant of why some people are not paying. Ok, this is one hypothesis." (E30) "I assume that it can be a difference between Amount for example, paid and Amount counted." (E28)	Screen: Map view, Supporting materials Possible keywords: "I am thinking the following hypothesis and considering the following hypothesis...", "my first hypothesis is...", "I assume tha...", "So I guess...", "For me it suggests..."
Test hypotheses	Checking hypotheses using available process mining techniques.	NA	Preceding mandatory activity: Generate hypotheses Screen: Filter
Assess results	Evaluating the findings against previously defined hypothesis or goal.	"There are actually quite a lot of cases where there was a payment in the dataset, there was no value for the Payment Amount." (E16)	Preceding mandatory activity: Test hypotheses or Create artifact Screen: Filtered map
Conclude	Providing a final answer to the question or its part.	"So, most of the fines are legitimate. The majority behaves in a way that is more legitimate, but there are some cases, like I said, that either they paid and then received a penalty or received the appeal and did not receive an answer to it, but received a	Defining and validating of PM analysts' strategies Screen: Writing down the conclusions Possible keywords: "I want to summarize..."

		penalty. These are actually the illegitimate situations.” (S5) “So, very... it seems that a very popular reason is that probably the organization is not sending on time the notification of the fine...” (E30) “ So I believe we had two circumstances , right, that we identified. So, one was ... I should write this down ...” (E16)	“I’m writing this down...”, “maybe this is a first answer to the question...”, “very popular reason...”, “we had two circumstances...”.
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Table 3: Analysis protocol describing the cognitive steps of the PEM4PPM v2 model, their explanation, example statement, and detection method; E# - experienced analyst’s ID; S# - student’s ID.

An example of the coding of two experienced analysts according to the steps of the PEM4PPM model is provided in [Example Coding](#) Section of this document.

Additional findings that were made during Stage 2 related to strategies applied by PM analysts (see **Section 5** Subsection Qualitative analysis paragraph *Identifying and validating PM analysts’ strategies*). After the strategies were identified we made an assessment of the analysts’ performance that was expressed in grades on a scale from 0 to 100. Both students and experienced analysts were asked to analyze the Road Traffic Fine Management Process log [1].

Students were asked to answer the question "Describe two to three circumstances in which a penalty is added. Is the penalty addition always legitimate, i.e., do people that receive a penalty deserve it?". **Table 4** presents a protocol for assessing the students’ performance.

#	Question parts	Criteria	Points
1	Describe two to three circumstances in which a penalty is added.	X main circumstances (Insert fine notification, Appeal to judge, Appeal to prefecture) and/or Y secondary circumstances (all other circumstances except X) were described, X, Y = 0,1,2,3...	$\max\{(X*10 + Y*2), 30\}$
2	Is the penalty addition always legitimate, i.e., do people that receive a penalty deserve it?	The answer is correct (“the penalty is not always legitimate) and had: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • right justification (e.g., relates to rules - temporal constraints that define legitimacy of the penalty) • partially correct justification • wrong justification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 70 • 20 • 10

Table 4: Protocol for assessing the students’ performance

Experienced analysts were asked to answer the question "Can you describe the three most prevalent circumstances (situations) in which the fines and the related expenses are not paid (in full) in this process? For each circumstance, if possible from the information at your disposal, can you provide at least one reason that explains why the fines are not paid (in full)?". **Table 5** presents a protocol for assessing the experienced analysts' performance.

#	Question parts	Points
1	Please, indicate the *first* circumstance you found.	30
2	Please, indicate the reason for the *first* circumstance.	3
3	Please, indicate the *second* circumstance you found.	30
4	Have you found a reason for the *second* circumstance?	3
5	Please, indicate the third circumstance you found. [Write "none" if you haven't found any circumstance]	30
6	Have you found a reason for the *third* circumstance?	3
7	Please, sort the circumstances above by prevalence (based on event frequency).	1

Table 5: Protocol for assessing the experienced analysts' performance

Table 6 presents the students, the strategies applied by them and their grades. **Table 7** presents the experienced analysts, the strategies applied by them and their grades.

S#	Strategy	Grade
1	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	100
2	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	92
3	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	80
4	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	50
5	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	50
6	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	50
7	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	50
8	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - NO testing (WWN)	50
9	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	50
10	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	40
11	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	40
12	NO interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (NNN)	40
13	NO interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (NNN)	34
14	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	32
15	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	30
16	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - NO testing (WWN)	30

Table 6: Students, applied strategy and grades.

S#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection

E#	Strategy	Grade
35	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	93
7	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	91
10	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	90
11	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - NO testing (WWN)	90
16	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	63
29	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	63
26	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	63
30	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - WITH testing (WWW)	61
3	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	61
6	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	60
28	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - NO testing (WWN)	30
22	WITH interpret data - NO hypotheses - NO testing (WNN)	3
34	WITH interpret data - WITH hypotheses - NO testing (WWN)	0

Table 7: Experienced analysts, applied strategy and grades.
E#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection

Analysis and Findings for RQ2

In order to test hypotheses 1-3, we conducted the **Mann-Whitney test** (also known as the Wilcoxon test for independent samples) [2]. This test is used to compare differences between two independent groups when the dependent variable is either ordinal or continuous, but not normally distributed. Before applying this test, we have to check that the data meet all required **assumptions**: (i) the sample size is small ($n < 30$); (ii) the samples are independent; (iii) the dependent variable (grade) is measured at the continuous level; (iv) the independent variable (strategy category) consists of two categorical, independent groups.

It is important to note that hypotheses 1-3 are one-tailed, therefore the two-tailed p-value of the output was divided by 2 to get the one-tailed p-value.

Calculation of effect sizes

Effect size was calculated manually, using the following formula: $r = Z / \sqrt{N}$.

According to Cohen's classification of effect sizes which is 0.1 (small effect), 0.3 (moderate effect) and 0.5 and above (large effect).

Hypothesis Statement 1

H0: analysts (students and experienced) who use the WWW strategy have lower/the same performance (grades) than analysts using other strategies.

H1: analysts (students and experienced) who use the WWW strategy have higher performance (grades) than analysts using other strategies.

Decision Rule: Reject H0 if p-value $< \alpha$ (0.05)

Mann-Whitney Test

Ranks			
category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
grade WWW	10	23.15	231.50
other	19	10.71	203.50
Total	29		

Test Statistics ^a	
	grade
Mann-Whitney U	13.500
Wilcoxon W	203.500
Z	-3.762
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Exact Sig. (2-tailed Sig.)	.000 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: category
b. Not corrected for ties.

0.000037
b. Not corrected for ties.

Fig. 1. Output of Mann-Whitney test for hypothesis statement (1)

			Percentiles						
category			5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	grade	WWW	50.00	51.10	62.50	85.00	92.25	99.30	
		other	00	3.00	30.00	40.00	50.00	63.00	
Tukey's Hinges	grade	WWW			63.00	85.00	92.00		
		other			31.00	40.00	50.00		

Fig. 2. Descriptive Statistics for hypothesis statement (1)

Effect size: $r = -3.762/\sqrt{29} = -0.699$

Conclusion: H0 is rejected, and concluded that the grades of analysts using the WWW strategy (median: 85; Q1: 62.50 - Q3: 92.25) are significantly higher than the grades of those using other strategies (median: 40; Q1: 30.00 - Q3: 50.00), with a large effect size (U = 13.5, Z = -3.762, p-value = .0000185, d = -0.699).

Hypothesis Statement 2

H0: students who use the WWW strategy have lower/the same performance (grades) than students using other strategies.

H1: students who use the WWW strategy have higher performance (grades) than students using other strategies.

Decision Rule: Reject H0 if p-value < α (0.05)

Mann-Whitney Test

Ranks			
category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
grade WWW	4	13.88	55.50
other	12	6.71	80.50
Total	16		

Test Statistics ^a	
	grade
Mann-Whitney U	2.500
Wilcoxon W	80.500
Z	-2.688
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.007
Exact Sig. (2-tailed Sig.)	.004 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: category

b. Not corrected for ties.

Fig. 3. Output of Mann-Whitney test for hypothesis statement (2)

			Percentiles						
		category	5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	grade	WWW	50.00	50.00	57.50	86.00	98.00	.	.
		other	30.00	30.00	32.50	40.00	50.00	50.00	.
Tukey's Hinges	grade	WWW			65.00	86.00	96.00		
		other			33.00	40.00	50.00		

Fig. 4. Descriptive Statistics for hypothesis statement (2)

Effect size: $r = -2.688/\sqrt{16} = -0.672$

Conclusion: H0 is rejected, and concluded that the grades of students using the WWW strategy (median: 86; Q1: 57.50 - Q3: 98.00) are significantly higher than the grades of those using other strategies (median: 40; Q1: 32.5 - Q3: 50.00), with a large effect size ($U = 2.5$, $Z = -2.688$, $p\text{-value} = .002$, $d = -0.672$).

Hypothesis Statement 3

H0: experienced analysts who use the WWW strategy have lower/the same performance (grades) than experienced analysts using other strategies.

H1: experienced analysts who use the WWW strategy have higher performance (grades) than experienced analysts using other strategies.

Decision Rule: Reject H0 if $p\text{-value} < \alpha$ (0.05)

Mann-Whitney Test

Ranks			
category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
grade WWW	6	9.50	57.00
other	7	4.86	34.00
Total	13		

Test Statistics ^a	
	grade
Mann-Whitney U	6.000
Wilcoxon W	34.000
Z	-2.161
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.031
Exact Sig. (2-tailed Sig.)	.035 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: category

b. Not corrected for ties.

Fig. 5. Output of Mann-Whitney test for hypothesis statement (3)

Percentiles

			Percentiles						
			5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	grade	WWW	61.00	61.00	62.50	76.50	91.50		
		other	.00	.00	3.00	60.00	63.00		
Tukey's Hinges	grade	WWW			63.00	76.50	91.00		
		other			16.50	60.00	62.00		

Fig. 6. Descriptive Statistics for hypothesis statement (3)

Effect size: $r = -2.161/\sqrt{13} = -0.599$

Conclusion: H0 is rejected, and concluded that the grades of experienced analysts using the WWW strategy (median: 76.50; Q1: 62.50 - Q3: 91.50) are significantly higher than the grades of those using other strategies (median: 60; Q1: 3.00 - Q3: 63.00), with a large effect size (U = 6, Z = -2.161, p-value = .0175, d = -0.599).

Hypothesis Statement 4

H0: the level of expertise (student vs experienced analyst) and the choice of strategy (WWW vs any other strategy) are independent.

H1: the level of expertise (student vs experienced analyst) and the choice of strategy (WWW vs any other strategy) are not independent.

In order to check whether selecting WWW or any other strategy is independent of being a student or an experienced analyst (hypothesis 4), we conducted the Chi-Squared Test of Independence of Categorical Variables [3]. It is a statistical test used to check whether some categorical variables are statistically independent in a population.

Even though a nonparametric statistic does not require a normally distributed population, there still are some restrictions regarding its use. Therefore, before applying the Chi-Squared Test of Independence of Categorical Variables, we checked that the data met all required assumptions: (i) two categorical variables (strategy category and participant group); (ii) two or more categories (groups) for each variable (strategy category: WWW, other; participant group: student, experienced analyst); (iii) independence of observations; (iv) relatively large sample size (expected frequencies for each cell are at least 1, and expected frequencies should be at least 5 for the majority (80%) of the cells).

Decision Rule: Reject H0 if p-value < α (0.05)

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
category * group	29	100.0%	0	0.0%	29	100.0%

category - group Crosstabulation

			group		Total
			student	experienced analyst	
category WWW	Count	4	6	10	
	% within category	40.0%	60.0%	100.0%	
	% within group	25.0%	46.2%	34.5%	
other	Count	12	7	19	
	% within category	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%	
	% within group	75.0%	53.8%	65.5%	
Total	Count	16	13	29	
	% within category	55.2%	44.8%	100.0%	
	% within group	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.421 ^a	1	.233		
Continuity Correction ^b	.639	1	.424		
Likelihood Ratio	1.423	1	.233		
Fisher's Exact Test				.270	.212
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.372	1	.242		
N of Valid Cases	29				

a. 1 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.48.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Fig. 4. Output of Chi-Squared Test of Independence of Categorical Variables for hypothesis statement (4)

Conclusion: H0 is not rejected ($\chi (1)^2 = 1.421$, p-value = .233) and concluded that the choice of the WWW strategy over another does not depend on being a student or an experienced analyst.

Example Coding

An example of coding of two experienced analysts according to the steps of the PEM4PPM v2 model is provided in the tables below, where **Text** - verbal utterances of the participants transcribed to the text (empty text appears in the cases where the action, for example, “filtering”, was performed by the participant in the PM tool without explaining it); **PEM4PPM v2 model step** - one of the steps of the PEM4PPM v2 model (see [Table 3](#)); **Date and Time** - date and time; **Log activity** - an action that the participant performed in the PM tool (this information was taken from the log produced by PM tool); **Attribute of the activity** - additional information about the action performed by participants in the PM tool (this information was not reflected in the PM tool’s log and was obtained from the screen recording of the session).

Coding of E30, #E - Experienced analyst

Text	PEM4PPM v2 model step	Date and Time	Log Activity	Attribute of the activity
We first need to see the definition of the activities and of the attributes.	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:00:05		
So, the activities are here. I will spend one minute or two just looking at them. Yeah. I don't see any differentiation between partial payment or full payment, but I guess that will appear somehow in the process. So, the interesting... the activity of interest is payment, of course. Now the attributes, ok, we have the PaymentAmount and the TotalPaymentAmount. So, maybe that'll give us an idea of if someone is paying fully the fine or not.	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:00:06		
Expense, all the expenses included in your questions? I mean, if I pay just the amount, but I don't pay the additional expenses, am I considered eligible? Is this an eligible case or not?	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:00:07		
Ok, clear. I don't. I also have some temporal constraints here.	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:02:24		
Ok, now I will turn to Disco. Of course, I can maximize this. Ok, the first job that I always do is to... to load the data of course, and have a quick and dirty view of the process at a low detail level. So, but at zero percent, it's a nice start to get a first impression and I'm trying to find a happy path here.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:02:23	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	

And I see that payment is the end of the process. There are... Ok, I will change this to case frequency, actually, because absolute frequency can be misleading sometimes [unintelligible].	Explore	28/6/2021 00:03:37		Frequency: case frequency
Now, I see that the total number of cases is 150, and the payment has only happened, what is written, there is a very small font but 69 and so it's a pretty big difference. So, we have a lot of payments that have not been realized. And of course, there is an appeal. But I see that there are not many appeals. So, I see that the [unintelligible] that are related to appeals, so I guess that maybe they could have a relief from the Payment. It's very small so there is just a very big number of payments that are not happening.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:04:11		
So, then I will try to gradually increase the detail level of the path and see if there is any big difference,		28/6/2021 00:04:12		
but I don't... ok the complexity of course, is bigger now, but I don't see any real structural differences in the process. Ok, there are some extra arrows, some extra transitions, but it seems that the structure is the same. One interesting thing that appeared is a loop here, the payment. It's interesting that indicates that this happening again and again, and this is something that we have missed if we have used the absolute frequency here, so with great frequency, I feel more safe.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:04:13		
Now, uh... Ok, normally I would have navigated the statistics and the cases ok, just to see some general statistics. But in this case, I'm looking for, for a quick response.		28/6/2021 00:06:18	Showing statistics view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
So, what I will do is create a filter of people that are not paying, so I will try to, I want to filter this activity. But I want to filter this, the opposite, I think this is the bottom in that selection. Ok, so I want all the others except the payment. So, I will now filter those cases that are not realizing any payments. Ok, so I am not sure yet that this is the correct filter, but I will try.	Focus	28/6/2021 00:06:19		

		28/6/2021 00:06:20	Filtered log in 1 sec, 844 millis	Attribute; Mandatory; X Payment
So, I see that this is 100% of the cases. Wow! Maybe I missed something, yeah. I didn't filter anything. Uh, ok, [unintelligible], so I wasn't using properly the filter,		28/6/2021 00:06:21	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
So, I want to remove all the cases that have one, at least one instance of payment just for that.	Focus	28/6/2021 00:06:22	Filtered log in 1 sec, 218 millis	Attribute; Forbidden; Payment
Ok, now I see that 53% of the cases are not paying. I will check again the structure. Send Fine. Ok, so maybe ...	Explore	28/6/2021 00:06:23	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Can I ask you something, [interviewer name]? Yes, this is not a preprocessed event log, I mean, incomplete cases are in, right?	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:06:24		
It could be the case, yes, because I see here that people that have not paid... Ok a lot of people in this activity Send for a lot of cases in this activity Send for Credit Collection, so maybe they will pay eventually, but not yet. Maybe we have the fines that are very fresh and are not included yet.	Interpret Data	28/6/2021 00:09:19		
So, let me check again, oh, sorry, what was the Send for Credit Collection? Uh ok, unpaid fines are sent [Reading]. Ah, ok, so this is not the case, so this is expected. Ok, Add Penalty.	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:09:21		
Ok, so I... if I remember well, that was not the frequent activity in the ... in the population, but let me check. I will return to the filter. Ok, and make this mandatory and see if the penalty is still a popular activity.	Generate hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:09:22		

		28/6/2021 00:09:26	Filtered log in 1 sec, 218 millis	Attribute; Mandator y; Payment
	Test hypotheses			
And I see that the penalty is not a popular activity in this case. I mean, ok, there are 20000 of Add Penalty, which is approximately one, less than 1/3 of the, of this population. While in the population of people that are not paying the penalty is more than 75 percent of the total population.	Assess Result	28/6/2021 00:09:27	Showin g map view for Road_T raffic_Fi ne_Man agemen t_Proce ss	
So, I guess this is an indication of the region, this activity, the Add Penalty, that means that when fines, when cases go through this activity, they are not paying.	Interpret Data	28/6/2021 00:09:28		
So, maybe giving them an extra Penalty, so I apologize, but I have to return to the definition of this Add Penalty, it is an additional penalty...	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:09:29		
Ok, so when, one hypothesis is that, when an additional penalty is applied, then people are not paid, but it can be the first it can maybe who are taken penalty because they are not paying.		28/6/2021 00:09:30		
So, we have to check for this, what comes first, Add Penalty or not paying that. In this case, maybe this diagram will be helpful. I mean, if they spent...	Explore	28/6/2021 00:12:37		
Oh, great. I am thinking the following hypothesis and considering the following hypothesis, if the penalty is because too many days have passed, then the penalty may be because of the delay.	Generate hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:12:38		
And so, I want to check the times here.	Test hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:12:39		
		28/6/2021 00:12:41		Performa nce: mean duration
And I see that it is 80 days, but I think it was, we have a normative constraint here, 90 days.	Test hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:12:42		
The fine notification must be sent within 90 days of the fine creation. And we have a medium and if the offender does not pay the fines within 60 days from being notified, Ok. So, this is the 60 days, Ok. This is a real, a realistic constraint.	Task understanding	28/6/2021 00:12:43		

Wow. Yes, this is very big, but I have to check with the opposite case. Let me check the priorities to see if time is different or not.	Test hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:12:44		
		28/6/2021 00:12:45	Filtered log in 1 sec, 218 millis	Attribute; Mandatory; Payment
Oh, nine, 89 days. Ok, so this is the usual, the typical response of the service. Ok, so I will start making... Sorry I have a connection error.	Test hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:12:46		
Ok, great.		28/6/2021 00:14:48		
So, normally I would spend more time trying to understand more about the differences in the flows and performance map between the two cases, the cases that have mandatory the payment activity and forbidden the payment activity and try to have some visual insights.		28/6/2021 00:14:55		
But now I will turn to the statistics. I have the filter applied and I will turn to the statistics and trying to, I don't know, seeing if there is any, something strange here.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:14:56	Showing statistics view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
So, I see that this resource of ... this is not the most popular. The empty resource is the most popular, so I guess this is not very relevant. The Amount, again we have a lot of empty values here. But I'm not sure why the value, the Amount is the same. I mean, it is a very critical attribute in a fine, so. But still, this is empty.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:14:57		
So, I will try to see what is the most popular level in every attribute, and then I will make the same with with the other group, with people that actually paid and check if there are any differences.	Refine goal	28/6/2021 00:16:22		
So, here in the vehicle class we have A... I'm very much concerned about these missing values in the payment. I mean, in the Amount and in the TotalPaymentAmount, that zero is that they don't... That the fine was for zero euros. And empty means....	Explore	28/6/2021 00:16:23		

Let's, let me return to the explanation of the attributes. I'm a bit lost here. The Amount should be paid for the fine. So, if this is empty, we have a critical element missing. Amount paid. A lot of missing values... Ok, the expense could be... Notification type. PaymentAmount.	Task understanding	28/6/2021 00:16:24		
So, I'm not sure. Ok, let's see the statistics of the other cases and then we can make some hypotheses.	Focus	28/6/2021 00:18:47		
	Focus	28/6/2021 00:18:48	Filtered log in 1 sec, 218 millis	Attribute; Mandatory; Payment
Ok, the amount is still blank here. So, this is not very critical. So, I'm not sure about this. I mean, 1/3 of the cases have a TotalPaymentAmount of zero. That means they are fine, but without any Amount and another 1/3 of the cases, they are fine, but we don't know the Amount. It's kind of strange. This is more or less distribution. I cannot sort something.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:18:49	Showing statistics view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
I mean, the distributions of the attributes does not seem very strange in [unintelligible] the other. Of course, I just make a quick check. I mean, if you check more, more thoughtlessly, maybe there will be probably... there will be some differences, but with just a quick look, I wasn't able to spot any difference.		28/6/2021 00:20:40		
So, I will delete the filter and try to return to the, try to return to the process		28/6/2021 00:20:41	>>> Filtering aborted	
Because I was not able to find any, any differences. Now, I will try to see cases that are escaping the payment and filter the path that escape, escapes the, this task. So, I will increase the, I will increase the the percentage of the path and try to find reasons why cases are escaping the, the payment.	Refine goal	28/6/2021 00:21:35	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Ok, so we have. Ok, this is a very popular arrow, very popular transition and the origin of this transition is Send for Credit Collection. So, after Send for Credit Collection, we go to and so I guess that, ok, they're	Explore	28/6/2021 00:21:36		

not paying. This is very expected. I mean, they're not paying. So, this is our Send for Credit Collection and that ends the case.				
So, I guess that we have violation of the deadline here. So, that, that seems to be a very popular reason, I mean, if I understood well the constraint here.	Interpret Data	28/6/2021 00:21:37		
They will collect... Oh no there is penalty. But I saw some explanation about the collection. What is Send for Credit Collection? Unpaid fines, but. We don't have any further.	Task Understanding	28/6/2021 00:21:38		
Another popular reason is this one and this one is..., the origin of the arrow is.... Oh, come on. I guess this is it, Send Fine. So, after the Send Fine we have thousands of cases here and we have 20000 cases that are not... There are no notifications for this.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:24:01		
So, my first hypothesis is this, that the delays in sending the notifications is a very popular variant of why some people are not paying. Ok, this is one hypothesis.	Generate hypotheses	28/6/2021 00:24:02		
So, very it seems that a very popular reason is that probably the organization is not sending on time the notification of the fine, and if I combine this with a normative constraint of 90 days, that the organization must send them to vacation within 90 days and the median time for the performance, I think it was 88 days or 89 days. So, it seems that, well, a lot of cases, a lot of people are not paying because the organization has not notified them that they should pay.	Conclude	28/6/2021 00:24:04		
So, I think this is a clear reason. I don't have any reason to doubt for that it seems a very plausible explanation. I mean, it's clear here 1000, 100000 fines and just 80000 notifications. So, and if I remember well, people that didn't pay at all were approximately 50000 or 60000 or something, so approximately 40% of the, of this population is because of a failure of our own business.	Conclude	28/6/2021 00:24:05		
So, another reason is the appeals, ok. The appeals are approximately 3000, ok. It's not that big, but it's not negligible. I mean, it's... if you consider that here we have a population, approximately 8000, it's five percent. So, it's, it's also, yes, an appeal.	Explore	28/6/2021 00:26:24		

<p>An appeal is also another reason of why people are not paying. Probably, I guess that this appeal opens a new process. So, these cases are monitored in another process, but for us, so eventually they pay, but maybe when they return, they are appearing as different case ID, so they don't appear at all. They are appearing in a different business process. So, we are losing approximately 40% from here and five percent from here.</p>	Conclude	28/6/2021 00:26:26		
<p>Now, the other thing that we are missing is why people that have been notified and did not appeal, they are not paying. So, this is the piece of the puzzle that we are missing. So, clearly, there is a penalty for them, but I'm not sure that the penalty is the reason or is the result of this not payment. I mean is the [unintelligible].</p>	Refine Goal	28/6/2021 00:27:35		
<p>So, I will try to filter this activity, the Add Penalty and try to find some...</p>	Focus	28/6/2021 00:27:36	Filtered log in 1 sec, 266 millis	Follower; Insert fine notification->Add penalty;
<p>I will return to the statistics, I don't have a lot of time, but I will return to the statistics, try to find out if there is anything special in this. Maybe they have a big Amount? No, I don't see any interesting things here. NIL is still the most popular vehicle class. Ok, I don't remember exactly the... So, this is very, very interesting for me, I mean, I have a TotalPaymentAmount of zero at a very great percent and then I have a penalty, but why should I have a penalty if I am not fined at all? I mean, I'm fined for zero. So, and also, this empty value is very annoying here. I mean, it's not helping to... to make or to make an analysis. I mean, obviously, there is something happening here, maybe zero, something that means something special for the business, but I cannot understand this right now. The article, points.</p>	Explore	28/6/2021 00:28:34	Showing statistics view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
<p>Ok, zero is, I mean, in all cases is the most popular, but I think that the percentage here is a bit larger. That means that people are not afraid of getting penalized with some points in their license, so maybe they don't care, so they are notified that I owe you zero euros. Zero points will be the penalty in my license, so why should I care? I don't see anything strange here. Notification type...</p>	Interpret Data	28/6/2021 00:28:35		

That's ok. So, I have, I have two hypotheses that explain half the cases, but I am missing the other half, which is probably equally interesting, but maybe I need a more detailed check. So, my... my two hypotheses are that ...		28/6/2021 00:31:14		
Ok, so should I stop sharing?		28/6/2021 00:31:49		

Coding of E26, #E - Experienced analyst

Text	PEM4PPM v2 model step	Date and Time	Log Activity	Attribute of the activity
Ok, all right,		28/7/2021 00:00:03		
Yeah, right. Ok, so first of all, I'll check this CSV file just to have an overview about the consistency of the data. Have a look on the event logs if they are consistent enough. And usually, we have two options. I can load everything in Disco and then do filtering in Disco, or maybe I can work on the file [CSV file] and do some cleaning here if I see some specific inconsistencies, inconsistencies, inconsistencies that would lead to problems during the upload.		28/7/2021 00:00:08		
But I guess that everything should be well and try the first upload. I open three sessions or more than one session for the analysis afterward, and again, I start with the load of the file. Ah, maybe I first moved the file on my Desktop.		28/7/2021 00:00:09		
Road traffic fines is called?		28/7/2021 00:02:09		
Oh here, thank you, well. Good. Ok, so now we check if the case ids are labeled correctly, looks like activities as well, the resources.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:02:22		
Seems to be Ok. Anonymized timestamps, they do not have a time, they have just a date. So, well, let's see what would happened. Variants, so let's label maybe the variants to see if we need them. Life-cycle transition could be also something that we should label. Matricola. Notification type, but interesting as well. PaymentAmount, let's take it. So, better to have some more information, uh. Then know what it is,	Explore	28/7/2021 00:02:23		

what we will see. Ok. Well, I would start now with this dataset here. No case I identified. Well, now it should be ok. Ready to start import. So, we started. So, it is part of a big list. It's always impressive how fast Disco does the import. Increase the process map. Ok.				
Ok, on the first look, it looks quite clean, so yeah let's have a look, let's zoom out a bit to have an overview about the whole map.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:04:40	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
We do not have a lot of different variants to have a look at the first step, something that we can also check here. We have 231 variants and we see that we have three main variants here, maybe four that are worth it to be analyzed. We have a lot of cases here as well.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:04:41	Showing log explorer view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Usually, I work with Pareto to have a better idea about the relevance, variants yeah... Dataset. Ok. [Commenting in their native language]		28/7/2021 00:06:25		
Maybe another check to, to do, first of all, is check the number of events that came in just to know if everything went well with the upload.		28/7/2021 00:06:26		csv file
Something that I should do first. Yeah, work well. Oh one is missing. Ah, that's the title. Ok, the import was fine.		28/7/2021 00:06:27	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
		28/7/2021 00:06:28	Filtered log	Variation; 91% of events
Ok, Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine, Fine Notification. So, it seems that the variant three contains variants that are not paid. All right. Good.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:06:29	Showing log explorer view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	Variant 1-7

			affic_Fine _Manage ment_Pro cess	
Ok. So, the question is to identify the flows that the, where the payment has not been done completely. That is why now I isolate the flows, the different flows that we have. And I have two options, one is to identify here the variants where I do not have any payments and then work with the filter and then save them. And the other option is to save,	Set Goal	28/7/2021 00:08:17		
click endpoints... Show me as a Create Fine, and the last event is payment, is payment here. Discard cases that end with Payment, should work, yeah. Then I should get just the ones that, the cases that do not have any payments inside and apply the filter.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:08:18	Filtered log	Endpoints; Discard cases; Create Fine -> Payment
Didn't work... I still have some with payments. I want these court cases.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:09:06	Showing log explorer view for Road_Tr affic_Fine _Manage ment_Pro cess	
		28/7/2021 00:09:07	Filtered log	Endpoints; Discard cases; Create Fine -> X Payment
Great, so we have also payment in between, Add Penalty and credit. Ok, that works like this.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:10:29	Showing log explorer view for Road_Tr affic_Fine _Manage ment_Pro cess	
Let's try something else. But the trend now is to sort out all cases that have a payment inside the flow.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:10:30		
So.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:10:31	Filtered log	Attribute; Forbidden;

				Payment
Oh, I didn't check how many. So, let's do something else. I would like to upload again the event log list and have another in window the initial situation in order to be able to compare the different scenarios.	Refine goal	28/7/2021 00:11:27	Showing statistics view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
We have 150000 cases, 150270 cases. Ok, we have 80655 cases without payment. And if we have a look to the variants, oh we have 79, uh? [Commenting in their native language] Exactly. Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification, Add Penalty, Send for Credit Collection. 70 percent of the cases, they send it, and even if a...	Explore	28/7/2021 00:11:28	Showing log explorer view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Send for Credit Collection, is this the company that is responsible to do the collection of the money?	Task Understanding	28/7/2021 00:11:29		
Send for Credit Collection. And 56282 cases. Then, here the second case is that we have 20385 cases corresponds to 25 percent, send the file, send the fine, and the payment is not coming in, so one, two. Then the third variant,	Explore	28/7/2021 00:13:52		Variant 1-3
what's the Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture?	Task Understanding	28/7/2021 00:13:53		
Ok, good.		28/7/2021 00:15:14		
Appeal is [Commenting in their native language], Ok. Ok, good. I understand. Ok, so that's the reason the offender is not, does not agree with the fine		28/7/2021 00:15:56		
and we have 2400 cases. 3.1%. Uh, appeal. So, let's have a look at the other ones. Appeal to Judge.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:15:57		Variant 3
So, now identified the three main process flows. We have one using this company that does collect the money, then we have another process where the fine is sent directly to the offender without using this collector company at that stage of the process. And then we have a third flow where we do the appeal in the prefecture.	Interpret Data	28/7/2021 00:17:14	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
So, what I would do now is to split the three processes. Probably it's not necessary to have here	Refine goal	28/7/2021 00:17:15		

the other ones.				
So, I do that here. Ok, I have to think and to endpoint filter, we have I would say I would like to see all cases that start with Create Fine, and end with Send Fine.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:17:16	Filtered log	Endpoints; Trim longest; Create Fine -> Send Fine
But we still have the Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture. I don't want to see them.		28/7/2021 00:17:17	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Now as a next filter I say forbidden all cases that contain appeal, appeal to Judge, Insert Date Appeal, Notify Result Appeal to Offender.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:17:18	Filtered log	Attribute; Forbidden;
Uh [Commenting in their native language] sorry.		28/7/2021 00:17:19	No case passed your filters	
Do you think? Oh really? I lost my filters, oK. Ah, also what did I do? Explore. Create it again. Start with Create Fine.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:19:55	Filtered log	Endpoints; Discard cases; Create Fine-> X Payment
Sorry I have to reconstruct my scenario. I lost it, I pushed the wrong button.		28/7/2021 00:22:16		
Ok, and how much time do I have?		28/7/2021 00:22:23		
Ok. Alright, now, I would like to show... Ok. Case one Send Fine,	Focus	28/7/2021 00:22:40	Filtered log	Attribute; Keep selected; Send Fine, Create Fine,Add penalty
Ok. So, I save now the first scenario of the process	Create Artifacts	28/7/2021 00:22:41		

that I have, apply filter, copy filter, apply filter. It Send Fine, Create Fine. Ok, then I use my... I can use the same button here. The second one is filter, click attribute, keep selected, we want to see the one where we have the collector, so we have to take out, Appeal to Judge, Insert Fine Notification. Notify this, this, and this, so we should have then and the payment. Apply filter, so they should to one,	Focus	28/7/2021 00:25:24	Filtered log	Attribute; Keep selected; Add penalty, Create fine, Insert fine notification , Send fine, Send for credit collection
so it should be the... the flow with the cases that are treated by the credit collection company.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:25:25	Showing map view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
Create Fine.	Explore	28/7/2021 00:25:26	Showing log explorer view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	Variant 1-4
Ok, so now I set an end-point filter to see all cases that end with Send for Credit Collection,	Focus	28/7/2021 00:27:16		
		28/7/2021 00:27:17	Filtered log	Endpoints; All -> Send for credit collection
and what I would do now is to filter out the one that has payment inside.	Focus	28/7/2021 00:27:18		
		28/7/2021 00:27:19	Filtered log	Attribute; Keep selected; X Payment

<p>So, now we should have just the ones that have not have been paid. And go over this and we have all the ones with Appeal to Judge. But I keep them. Because they are apparently correct, the fines are correct and they go on and are sent to this company to be collected. So, this would be my second case. Copy and filter. Just collect, collect, create</p>	Create Artifacts	28/7/2021 00:27:20	Showing log explorer view for Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process	
<p>and then we have the third scenario with the appeal to be interesting to be checked. The. Oh, that's the wrong one. Uh.</p>	Explore	28/7/2021 00:27:21		
<p>Yeah, I just was having a look at the question.</p>	Task Understanding	28/7/2021 00:30:54		
<p>To try to answer the question, though. Ok, is the question inside here somewhere or is it in the data file?</p>	Task Understanding	28/7/2021 00:31:02		
<p>Here in artifacts, no here. Yeah, sorry. Why? Can open it. Can you describe the three most prevalent situations which the fines aren't paid in full?</p>	Task Understanding	28/7/2021 00:31:32		
<p>Ok, well, I have identified them and so from my point of view, I have the three that I mentioned before. I have the one that is directly sent to the offender and not paid. Then I have the one that has been sent over to the collector, credit collector that is not paid yet. And then I have the one where the offender appeals to the prefecture because it is not, he does not agree with, with the cases. Now, the reason why do we have after, after my analysis, we have the question? Yes, I would write them down there.</p>	Conclude	28/7/2021 00:31:33		
<p>In the third, in the next step would have been to isolate the third process that I mentioned here, the one with the appeals, but due to my time limit, I don't do that right now. But I would follow more or less the same procedure as I have done for the other two. That would... that means that I would use the end-to-end filter and the attribute filter to isolate the cases that are using specific process steps.</p>		28/7/2021 00:32:44		

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